

Comparative Study of Efficacy and Safety of Ondansetron and Ramosetron in Patients undergoing Hysterectomy

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Abstract

Introduction: Nausea and vomiting have been associated for many years with the use of general and spinal Anaesthesia for surgical procedures. With the change in the emphasis from an inpatient to outpatient, hospital and office-based medical/surgical enhancement, there has been increased interest in the 'big little problem of PONV (Postoperative nausea and vomiting). The newest class of antiemetics used for prevention and treatment of PONV (Postoperative nausea and vomiting) are serotonin (5-HT₃) receptor antagonists—Ondansetron, Granisetron, Tropisetron, Dolasetron and Ramosetron. In the present study, intravenous ondansetron and Ramosetron were compared in the prevention of postoperative nausea and vomiting undergoing hysterectomy.

Material and Methods: This clinical study consisting of 100 adult patients slated to undergo elective surgeries was undertaken at Prakash Institute of Medical sciences and Research, Urun Islampur, and Hospital. In this randomized, single blind clinical trial, we studied 100 patients between the ages of 23- and 65-years undergoing hysterectomy under spinal anaesthesia. Approval was taken from the ethical committee and written informed consent was taken from all the patients. They were randomly divided into two groups. Group I: Patients included in this group will receive Inj. Ondansetron 4 mg just before surgery and after 12 hr. Group II: Patients included in this group will receive Inj. Ramosetron 0.3mg just before surgery only.

Results: In our study, in initial 6 hours total 17 patients had nausea out of which 9 belonged to group I and 8 belonged to group II. When these groups were compared the difference was statistically non-significant ($p > 0.05$). In next 6 to 24 hours 5 patients in group I and 4 in group II had nausea ($p > 0.05$). However when the incidence of nausea was compared after 24 hours in group I (5 patients) and group II (1 patient) the difference was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Total number of patients in group I reporting nausea was 19 while it was 13 in group II, when compared it was found that group II has significantly lesser ($p < 0.05$) occurrence of nausea.

Conclusion: We have found that antiemetic therapy with Ramosetron at a dose of 0.3 mg is safer, well-tolerated, proved more effective and cheaper than Ondansetron 4 mg in the prevention of PONV.

Keywords: Nausea, Vomiting, Ondansetron, Ramosetron.

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Introduction

Nausea and vomiting have been associated for many years with the use of general and spinal Anaesthesia for surgical procedures [1]. With the change in the emphasis from an inpatient to outpatient, hospital and office-based medical/surgical enhancement, there has been increased interest in the ‘big little problem’ [1] of PONV (Postoperative nausea and vomiting) [2].

However, inspite of these advances, nausea and vomiting still occur with unacceptable frequency in association with surgery and anaesthesia and the description of it as “the big little problem” encapsulates much of the general perception [3].

Over the years, numerous approaches have been used in the management of PONV (Postoperative nausea and vomiting). Various techniques including olive oil and insulin-glucose infusions were reported to be effective [3]. Robert Ferguson described the use of olive oil in 1912, he postulated that oil in the stomach “absorbed any ether that may be present there” [4]. The effect of atropine was appreciated by Brown – Sequard as early as 1883 when he wrote “in the very great majority of cases, the addition of a certain amount of atropine to morphine prevents the nausea and vomiting occurring with morphine alone [5].

Phenothiazines were synthesized originally in the late 19th century. In the late 1930s, promethazine was found to have antiemetic property. Charpentier synthesized chlorpromazine in 1949, but sedation and hypotension were limiting side-effects [6].

The traditional antiemetics include anticholinergics (scopolamine); Dopamine receptor antagonists which include the phenothiazines (promethazine), benzamides (metoclopramide) and butyrophenones

(droperidol) and benzodiazepines (midazolam and lorazepam). The non-traditional antiemetics include ephedrine, propofol and corticosteroids [7].

The newest class of antiemetics used for prevention and treatment of PONV (Postoperative nausea and vomiting) are serotonin (5-HT₃) receptor antagonists—ondansetron, granisetron, tropisetron, dolasetron and ramosetron [8-16].

In the present study, intravenous ondansetron and ramosetron were compared in the prevention of postoperative nausea and vomiting undergoing hysterectomy.

Material and Methods

This clinical study consisting of 100 adult patients slated to undergo elective surgeries was undertaken at Prakash Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Urun Islampur, single blind clinical trial, we studied 100 patients between the ages of 23 and 65 years undergoing hysterectomy under spinal anaesthesia. Approval was taken from the ethical committee and written informed consent was taken from all the patients. They were randomly divided into two groups.

Group I: Patients included in this group will receive Inj. Ondansetron 4 mg just before surgery and after 12 hr.

Group II: Patients included in this group will receive Inj. Ramosetron 0.3mg just before surgery only.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Female patients with 23 to 65 age groups undergoing hysterectomy, under spinal anaesthesia.
2. Patients willing to provide informed consent.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Critically ill patients.
2. Patients with pregnancy and lactation.
3. Patients with renal, hepatic, and cardiac diseases or on cardiac glycosides were excluded.
4. Patients who received radiotherapy, had gastro-intestinal occlusion, raised intra cranial tension, head injury,
5. Patients with they had experienced an allergic reaction to other antiemetics.
6. Patients taking drugs like-antipsychotics, sedatives, other antiemetics.

Preoperative visit was conducted on the previous day of surgery and a detailed history and present complaints were noted. General and systemic examinations of cardiovascular, respiratory and central nervous system were done. Routine laboratory investigations like complete haemogram, routine urine, blood urea, serum creatinine, and blood sugar, ECG, bleeding time and clotting time were done.

Patients were transported to the recovery

Results**Table 1: Demography of Patients of Group I (Ondansetron) and Group II (Ramosetron)**

Parameter	Group I N=50	Group II N=50	p value
Age	47.7±8.55	47.3±8.62	p > 0.05
Weight	57.54 ±8.57	56.92 ±7.98	p > 0.05

Table 2: Mean Duration (In Minutes) of Surgery of Patients Of Group I (Ondansetron) and Group II (Ramosetron)

Groups	No. of cases	Mean Duration (Mins)	p value
Group I	50	107.20 ±23.01	p > 0.05
Group II	50	104.7 ±21.95	

Table 3: No. of Patients Complaining of Nausea in Postoperative Period in Patients of Group I (Ondansetron) and Group II (Ramosetron)

Duration	Group I	Group II	Total no of cases	p value
0-6 hour	9	8	17	p > 0.05
6-24 hours	5	4	9	p > 0.05
>24 hours	5	1	6	p < 0.01
Total	19	13	32	p < 0.01

room and later to the ward after confirming an adequate level of consciousness and intact reflexes. The incidences of PONV were recorded with in the first 0-6 hours, 6-24 hours and >24 hours. Episodes of PONV were identified by spontaneous complaints by the patients or by direct questioning. "Complete response" was defined as the absence of nausea, retching or vomiting and no need for rescue antiemetic during the > 24-hour observation period. Rescue antiemetic was provided with Inj. Metoclopramide 10mg i.v in the event of one or more episodes of vomiting depending on the observer's discretion.

Statistical Analysis

Quantitative data was analysed by 'Z test for difference between two means. Qualitative data was analysed by 'Chi-square' test. p value < 0.05 was taken as significant and p value < 0.001 was taken as highly significant while p value > 0.05 was considered as insignificant.

Table 4: No. of Patients Complaining of Retching in Postoperative Period in Patients of Group I (Ondansetron) and Group II (Ramosetron)

Duration	Group I	Group II	Total no of cases	P value
0-6 hour	07	05	12	p > 0.05
6-24 hours	03	02	05	p > 0.05
>24 hours	04	01	05	p < 0.01
Total	14	8	22	P < 0.01

Table 5: No. of Patients Complaining of Vomiting in Postoperative Period in Patients of Group I (Ondansetron) and Group II (Ramosetron)

Duration	Group I No. of cases	Group II No. of cases	p value
0- 6 hour	2+ 05	02	p > 0.05
	3+ 02	02	
6-24 hours	2+ 02	02	p > 0.05
	3+ 02	02	
>24 hours	2+ 05	02	p < 0.01
	3+ 01	01	
Total	17	11	p < 0.01

Table 6: No. of Patients Complaining of Nausea and Vomiting in Postoperative Period in Patients of Group I (Ondansetron) and Group II (Ramosetron)

Groups	No. of cases	PONV Present	P value
Group I	50	13	P < 0.01
Group II	50	05	
Total	100	18	

Table 7: Use of Rescue Medication in Post-Operative Period in Patients of Group I (Ondansetron) and Group II (Ramosetron)

Duration	Group I	Group II	No of patients needed rescue.	p value
0-6 hour	02	02	04	p > 0.05
6-24 hours	02	02	04	p > 0.05
>24 hours	04	01	05	p < 0.01
Total	08	05	13	p < 0.01

Table 8: Frequency of Adverse Drug Reaction Observed in Group I (Ondansetron) and Group II (Ramosetron)

Adverse Effects	Group I	Group II	Total	P value
Headache	6	4	10	p > 0.05
Dizziness	1	1	2	p > 0.05
Rashes & allergic reactions	1	1	2	p > 0.05

Discussion

In our study, in initial 6 hours total 17 patients had nausea out of which 9 belonged to group I and 8 belonged to group II. When these

groups were compared the difference was statistically non-significant (p > 0.05). In next 6 to 24 hours 5 patients in group I and 4 in

group II had nausea ($p>0.05$). However, when the incidence of nausea was compared after 24 hours in group I (5 patients) and group II (1 patient) the difference was found to be statistically significant ($p<0.05$). Total number of patients in group I reporting nausea was 19 while it was 13 in group II, when compared it was found that group II has significantly lesser ($p<0.05$) occurrence of nausea.

Junghee Ryu [17] found that 13 patients had nausea in Group I (Ondansetron, $n=40$) and 10 patients had nausea in Group II (Ramosetron, $n=40$) in initially 0-6 hrs, while next 6- 24hrs 4 patients had nausea in Group I and 2 patients had nausea in Group II. After 24 hrs, 8 patients had nausea in Group I and 5 patients had nausea in Group II. *Fujii Y et al* [18] found that 7 patients had nausea in Group I and 4 patients had nausea in Group II in initially 0-6 hrs, while next 6- 24hrs 6 patients had nausea in Group I and 4 patients had nausea in Group II. After 24 hrs, 10 patients had nausea in Group I and 3 patients had nausea in Group II.

In our study table 4 shows the number of patients reporting postoperative retching. In initial 6 hours total 12 patients had retching out of which 7 belonged to group I and 5 belonged to group II. When these groups were compared the difference was statistically non-significant ($p>0.05$). In next 6 to 24 hours 3 patients in group I and 2 in group II had retching ($p>0.05$).

However, when the incidence of retching after 24 hours was compared in group I (4 patients) and group II (1 patient) the difference was found to be statistically significant ($p<0.05$). Total number of patients in group I reporting nausea was 14 while it was 8 in group II, when compared it was found that group II has significantly lesser ($p<0.05$) occurrence of retching.

The findings of studies conducted by *Junghee Ryu* [17] and *Fujii Y et al* [18] consistent

with our study who noted that when both groups were compared to each other the incidence of postoperative retching in initially 0-24 hrs. period, there were no statistically significant differences. But when both groups were compared > 24 hrs. Group II had significantly lesser incidence of postoperative retching.

In current study table 5 shows the number of patients having postoperative vomiting. Patients were classified according to severity as +2 (1-episode of vomiting), +3 (2-episode of vomiting), +4 (3-episode of vomiting) In initial 6 hours 7 patients had vomiting once out of which 5 belonged to group I and 2 belonged to group II, while 4 patients had vomiting two times out of which 2 belonged to each group. When these groups were compared the difference was non- significant ($P>0.05$). In next 6 to 24 hours 4 had vomiting once out of which 2 belonged to each group. While 4 patients had vomiting two times out of which 2 belonged to each group. However, when the incidence of vomiting after 24 hours was compared 7 had vomiting once out of which 5 belonged to group I and 2 belonged to group II.

In our study, table 7 shows the numbers of patients receiving the rescue medicine as and when needed basis. Inj. Metoclopramide was given as rescue medicine to 4 patients initially 0- 6 hrs. Out of which 2 belonged to each group. While in next 6- 24 hours 4 patients had received rescue medicine, out of which 2 belonged to each group. However, when the use of rescue medicine after 24 hours was compared 4 belonged to group I and 1 belonged to group II.

Another study of *S. I. Kim and S. C. Kim et al.* [19] found that the consumption of rescue drug in the ramosetron group in 0-6hrs,6-24 hrs and >24 hrs was (Ramosetron Vs Ondansetron: 6 Vs 9,3 Vs 7,8 Vs 16 respectively) markedly less than that of ondansetron group at postoperative >24 hrs.

Table 8 shows the adverse drug reactions seen in patients. In group I, 6 had headache, 1 had dizziness, 1 had rash while the incidence in group II was 4, 1, 1 respectively. These values were comparable to each other ($p > 0.05$). We could not differentiate that these adverse drug reactions seen whether due to prophylactic antiemetic drugs or due to other anaesthetic drugs. Jeong-Hun Suh, M.D [20] and S. I. Kim and S. C. Kim *et al* [19] stated that there were no statistically significant differences in the incidence of adverse events among the Ramosetron group and Ondansetron group. The most frequently reported adverse events were dizziness and headache.

As Inj. Ondansetron was given 2 times in group I and Inj. Ramosetron once in group II, therefore patients' compliance was better in Group II. In our study, ramosetron was shown to be as effective as ondansetron in preventing nausea and vomiting during the first 24 h in female patients after hysterectomy.

However, ramosetron was more effective in preventing nausea and vomiting and decreasing the severity of nausea after the 24 hr. Ramosetron therapy was less costly and also shown to be effective in reducing the need for additional rescue antiemetics after surgery. So Ramosetron may be favoured over Ondansetron in prevention of post-operative nausea and vomiting.

Conclusion

PONV is one of the most distressing side-effects of anaesthesia and surgery with a high incidence following spinal anaesthesia. The quest for more effective antiemetic drugs without the potential for sedative or extrapyramidal side-effects has led to the development of a relatively new class of drugs, 5-HT₃ antagonists of which ondansetron is a prototype. The need for drugs with improved performance within this group arose on account of relatively less

potency and shorter duration of action, besides detectable binding to other 5-HT receptors by ondansetron. Ramosetron is another a potent and highly selective 5-HT₃ receptor antagonist.

We have found that antiemetic therapy with Ramosetron at a dose of 0.3 mg is safer, well-tolerated, proved more effective and cheaper than Ondansetron 4 mg in the prevention of PONV.

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